

Parental Encouragement in Vocational Choice of Senior Secondary School Students of Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract Encouragement will always have a very positive effect. Successful parents often use words of encouragement to show their children how to make improvements. The study is conducted to explore the parental encouragement in vocational choice of the senior secondary school of Jammu and Kashmir. The sample is selected from senior secondary school student of Jammu. Total of 100 students was selected randomly for the study. Data is collected using APES Aggarwal parental encouragement scale which was modified by the investigator. The study revealed that there is no significant difference between boys and girls in parental encouragement in vocational choice of senior secondary school student. There is significant difference parental encouragement in vocational choice between urban and rural students of the senior secondary school of Jammu and Kashmir. There is also significantly different parental encouragement in vocational choice between government and private school of the student.

Keywords Parent, Encouragement, Vocational, Senior Secondary Students.

Introduction The world is becoming competitive and quality of performance is the key factor for personal progress, parenting is the family enrolment process that consists of parent's attitudes, values. Many factors affect the vocational choice parental encouragements are essential to the way children feel about themselves. On the other hand, if parents encourage a child's move toward self-confidence. Parental Encouragement is the essential factor in giving the life of a present generation. This is because the norms of society are learned by the child, first in the family and then at school. In encouragement, the parents help the child, guide him and coax him so that he may not feel disheartened at a particular point of difficulty.

Encouragement shall always have a positive effect. Successful parents regularly use words of encouragement to show their children how to make an improvement. They show their affection and cheer their children on to perform at their best. They offer encouragement and support, even when the child performances failed. These parents understand that their children will not be good at everything. Thus, they encourage their children to explore their interests, do their best and try to learn how to do better next time. In the adolescence period, children have interest in life career has often become a source of great concern. At this time, adolescents learn to differentiate among vocational choices as well as vocational preferences. During this period the child becomes alert to their interest and disinterest and needs proper direction or path in choosing the right vocation of their choice. Parents should act as a living model. It gives them more confidence, right direction, right path, and energy also. Parent's encouragement is the backbone of the individual's life. Parental Encouragement is not only important for the individual present development but also helps in making right decisions for right vocation.

Parental Encouragement

Parental Encouragement means guiding the children in such a way that they are not disheartened. It may be approving his/her work or suggesting some modifications or better ways to do a particular work in a rational manner so that the child can actually see the benefits. Imposing forcefully our own methods without explaining their benefits can lead to avoidance and discouragement in children's. The parents play an important role in shaping a child's personality. The loving and accepting parents provide a healthy medium to the child to grow his energies into proper channels and exercise his potentialities to the maximum so that the child becomes a productive member of the society in which he has to live and becomes a mentally healthy person. Parental encouragement has great significance in developing psychological as well as the academic behaviours of a children, shaping the attitudes and achievement patterns of a children. Parents are the ones who always want their children to be successful human beings and encourage them

for the same. It gives them more confidence and energy. Parental encouragement is one of the aspects of the parent treatment pattern. In recent year, to improve the quality of education and their career choice, the parent help and guide them so that the students may not feel disheartened at a particular point difficulty. Parent participation in school activities can enhance student's learning behaviours and also lower down their workload. Every parent wants their children should stand better in their academic and this can be only parents themselves show the encouragement toward education.

Parental encouragement may be different from society to society culture to culture. Parental encouragement may have different types, which may have a differential influence on the academic performance of their children. Parents encourage has a greater impact on students' educational outcomes. It may include activities like helping children in reading, encouraging them to do their homework autonomously, guiding their activities inside the house and outside of their house and providing coaching services for improving their learning in different subjects. Adolescent period is one of the most crucial and critical as well. It is during this time that adolescent struggle with their own identity. They are growing into a period of maturation and development that is terrifying and unknown. They need direction and strong support features that come from their parents.

Nature of the parental encouragement varies according to the age level period of growth of the child. As the child grows, his needs, capacities, and interest go on changing and the parents encourage their children accordingly. As high school students contemplate college and attempt to navigate the challenges of high school life, parents must be clear about their role. The primary role of a parent is to consistently offer love, encouragement, support, and guidance.

Importance of Parental Encouragement

The participation of parents contributes towards the academic achievement of their children and such participation has many positive consequences for the family, the school and especially for the senior secondary students. Parental encouragement is a necessary tool to increase the academic achievement of senior secondary students' parents can encourage their children in the following manner:

1. Parents can encourage their children by understanding their strengths and weaknesses. All children are unique even in the same family, one child may love math and find it easy, while others find it a challenge. So the parents should understand their capacities and then accordingly encourage them.
2. The parents should praise their children's efforts as well as their accomplishment. Parents should find time for one on one conversation with their child. They should teach their child how to set goals.
3. Parent should help in future career selection and should ask their children what they want to be in future. E.g. A child, who want to become an engineer or doctor, needs to take science and math course at the secondary level. Parents should help their child to understand that if they do not have a specified career goal, the decision they make now can affect their future. Encourage them to take the challenging course. Thus with a little caring and creativity, parents can help children, and to prepare for a bright future after secondary level.

Vocational Choice

Vocational choice has been regarded as an integral aspect of human life because life is considered incomplete without it. It has a great emotional significance for a person besides the material advantages it bestows on one. Without any vocation, life is considered incomplete. An individual has to be engaged in some kind of vocation to live in the society, to fulfil the need and necessities of the family, today is said to be an age of science and technology. Fast advancement made by man in scientific technology and industrial fields has immediately influenced all aspects of man's life and due to scientific advancement, division of labor and specialization of function, modern society demands the fullest use of skilled man power at all levels.

Vocational choices are a developmental process and span almost through person's lifetime. Vocational choices development leads to choice, which processes starts from primary school. Vocational choices could also be defined as a sequence of positions, jobs or occupation, which a person engages in during his working life. Vocational takes a sensible amount of years within a particular occupation, for example, ten, fifteen and twenty year's duration.

Factor influencing the choice of careers

1. **Physical Factors:** In several occupations such as defense, police, security-related occupations, physical characteristics like height, weight and general physical endurance matters. In some other, like driving occupations, proper eyesight is required. The factors relating to a general physique like height, weight, eyesight, hearing, speech, general health, any handicap all have a place in choosing a career.
2. **Psychological Factors:** These factors are interests, attitudes, aptitudes, general intelligence and personality characteristic. Wherever parents insist upon their children to take up a particular job in which the child himself is not interested, nonadjustment takes place. Many jobs also require particular types of personality traits. For example, for public relation job, a person should be outgoing and should

have good communication skills. In the absence of these, one should not aspire to such occupation.

3. **Economic Factors:** These factors include the economic status of the family, and whether the family can afford the training and the education for the child to pursue a particular career. On the demand side, the scope of employment, and self-employment future trends of the economy, technical advancements, legislation, all have their influence.
4. **Social Factors:** Traditions and cultural influence, social obligations, social needs, and demands make an impact on the choice of career.
5. **Family Factors:** Parents outlook towards various jobs and their influence on the child, family status, parental aspirations, obligations towards family, needs of the family, family circumstances for taking up occupations outside city or country where the family is residing, are some of the factors that are responsible in career choice.
6. **Individual Demands and Value:** These factors relate to the individuals demands from occupations. These include the monetary benefits, other perks, the social security, like pension etc., the status of the job, profit, independence to take a decision, outlets for self- expressions, etc.
7. **Other Factor:** Other factors such as who would take decision for the child, availability of information about various jobs, chance factors etc. also affect career choice.

Objective of study

1. To compare the difference of parental encouragement in the vocational choice between parents of boys and girls students of senior secondary schools of Jammu & Kashmir
2. To study the difference in parental encouragement in the vocational choice between rural and urban senior secondary school students of Jammu & Kashmir
3. To compare the difference in parental encouragement in the vocational choice between government and private senior secondary school students of Jammu & Kashmir

Review of Literature

Agarwal (1986) conducted a study on the effect of parental encouragement on the educational development of student (secondary stage) find out that the parental encouragement and educational development were found to be positively correlated.

Poonam (2008) conducted a study of the relationship between parental encouragement and motivation of secondary school learners. The main objective of the study was to find out the difference if any in achievement motivation of boys and girls belonging to different levels of parental encouragement. The researcher reported that the girls are a higher degree of achievement motivation in comparison to the boy and better the parental encouragement better is the achievement.

Paloú.R & Drobot. L (2010) conducted a study on the impact of family influence on the career choice of adolescents. The study shows that Parents who are affectionate, tolerant, simulative and performance-oriented get more involved in the children's vocational development. Also, children with a securing attachment are more open to guidance, to vocational exploring.

Bhargava, (2012) conducted a study on, "Parental Encouragement and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students". The investigator used Survey method and used stratified random sampling technique. The sample was consists of 350 higher secondary school students from ten schools in Thanjavur district. The result found that there is a significant relationship between parental encouragement and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

Yadav (2013) conducted a study on academic achievement among high and low parental encouragement group of students. The main objective of the study was to study the impact of parental encouragement on the academic achievement of students. The study revealed that there was a significant difference in mean achievement scores of high and low parental encouragement group of students.

Rafiq et al (2013) conducted a study on parental involvement and academic achievement, a study on the secondary school of Lahore, Pakistan; the main objective of the study was to explore the effect of parental involvement in the academic achievement of their children. The study revealed that involvement has a significant effect on the better academic performance of the student.

Kumar and Negi (2013) conducted a study of academic achievement of a high school student in relation to their parental encouragement. The study shows that there is no relationship between the academic achievement and parental encouragement of high school students.

Sekar.P & Mani. S (2013), conducted the study on parental encouragement to higher secondary students in Thiruvannamalai District: Findings showed that the rural and urban higher secondary biology students have significantly differed in parental encouragement. Similarly, the higher secondary biology students belonging to Tamil and English medium also significantly differed in their parental encouragement.

Muneeswari. M. (2013), conducted a study to find out the parental encouragement of higher secondary students. The result revealed that the parental encouragement of higher secondary students is very high. There is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary students in their parental encouragement.

Kaur Jasraj (2013) conducted a study on parental encouragement in relation to academic achievement of the student. The result revealed that there is a significant difference between the academic achievements of the students receiving high and low parental encouragement. The students receiving high parental encouragement showed better academic achievement than the students receiving low parental encouragement.

P. Sekar (2013) conducted a study on parental encouragement in relation to academic achievement of the student. The result was revealed that rural and urban higher secondary biology students exist significant differed in parental encouragement. The urban higher secondary school students have gained more parental encouragement when compared to the parental encouragement of rural higher secondary school students.

Olaosebikan et.al (2014) conducted a study on effects of parental influence on adolescents' career choice in badagry local government area of Lagos state Nigeria. The results of the study seem to indicate that adolescents in secondary schools in Badagry local government Area of Lagos state have some form of independence in making career choices.

Jain Payal (2014) conducted a study on parental encouragement in career choice of secondary school student .it was found that significant gender differences existed in parental encouragement, whereas significant area differences were found in the parental encouragement among rural and urban respondents.

Sharma Anuradha (2014) found that there is a significant and positive relationship between parental encouragement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students. The study also indicates that there is a significant difference between male and female with regard to parental encouragement. The female students show greater parental Encouragement than male students.

Bindu.V & Aruna P.K (2014), aimed to find out the extent of the relationship between parental encouragement and process skill of secondary school students. Results showed that parental encouragement is positively related to process skill of adolescent students. The study also reveals that there is local and management difference exists for parental encouragement and process skill in social studies.

Mohamedayup khan. M & Mani. S (2014), aimed to find out the level of students personal problem, study involvement and academic achievement among the higher secondary school students. Results showed that gender has an impact on students' personal problems; study involvement and academic achievement are related to each other.

DR. Smriti Kiran Saimons (2016) conducted a study on the topic, the study of the impact of parental encouragement on vocational attitude maturity of adolescents the result shows that there is no significant correlation between the effect of parental encouragement and vocational attitude maturity among adolescents.

Dr. Najmah Peerzada and Masroof Yousuf (2016) conducted a study on rural and urban higher secondary school students: Their parental encouragement and academic achievement. The main objective was that to compare the academic achievement of male and female of rural and urban secondary school student and their parental encouragement. Data were collected (120 urban and 120 rural) from various higher secondary school student of district Srinagar and Pulwama.

Dr. A. S. Arul Lawrence & Dr. C. Barathi (2016) conducted a study on topic "parental encouragement in relation to academic achievement of higher secondary school students". The result shows that there is a significant relationship between parental encouragement and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

Singh, M (2016) conducted a study on the topic, "A study of academic achievement of high school students in relation to their parental encouragement" The investigator was used purposive sampling and 200 students were selected. Boys and girls of high schools do not differ significantly in their parental encouragement and the result revealed that there does not exist any significant relationship between the academic achievement and parental encouragement of high school students.

Kumar. S (2016) conducted a study on the topic, Career Choice and College Students: Parental Influence on Career Choice Traditionalism among College Students in Selected Cities in Ethiopia. It was found that there is a significant influence of parents on career choice among students. Specifically, fathers influence is found to be more significant on career choice decision making among students than their mothers.

Mwaa Mutinda Alphonse (2015) conducted on the study Parental Factors Influencing Career Choice among High School Students in Nairobi County The purpose of this study was to investigate the extent by which parental factors influence career choice among form four students in Nairobi County. The study also sought to establish the relationship and significance of this parental factors and the student career choice.

Zahra, Rita Rezaee (2016) conducted a study on the topic the influence of parenting style on academic achievement and career path. Among 1600 students, 310 students were selected randomly as the sample. There was a significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and educational success. Also, findings showed a significant relationship between firm parenting style and Career Path of the students, authoritarian parenting style and Career Path of the students, educational success and Career Path of the students.

Lawrence, A. S. Arul; Barathi, C (2016) conducted a study on parental encouragement in relationship to the academic achievement of higher secondary school students. The

result shows that there is a significant relationship between parental encouragement and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

Okesina, F. A., & Famolu, F. B. (2022). Conducted study on Parental Influence on Choice of Career among Secondary School Students in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. The findings of the study shown that parents encouragement towards students on making good career decisions, parents advising students about specific careers, and parents encouragement towards students on considering different education and career options were significant influences of parents' choice of career among secondary students in the Ilorin Metropolis. The research assumptions tested shown that there was no significant difference in the parental influence on choice of career among secondary school students in the Ilorin metropolis based on a parents level of education, occupation and family type.

Shilpi Datta, J. D. Milton 2023 Study on the effect of parental Influence on the Choice of careers and roles played in academic performance of student's Bangladeshi perspective. Study revealed that Influence of parents really matters in academic level of students. It is found that most of the parents support the choices of their children. Their support creates positive impact on the students. The parental motivation and inspiration is essential for proper development of a student. Creation of positive environment is really important to keep the students engaged in academic curriculum and it depends on parents. If the parents show positivity towards the students, the effect from students is also progressive. Creating pressure on the students does not create positive impact rather than it creates negative impact on their study. The students feel bore while doing study and when they do not get good result, they face stress from their surroundings.

Evi Schmid & Veerle Garrels (2021) Conducted a study on Parental involvement and educational success among vulnerable students in vocational education and training. The results from this study contribute to the field by describing the particular forms of parental involvement that matter in the eyes of students identified as vulnerable. Moreover, the results highlight the importance of identifying the particular needs of students and supporting all parents as empowered participants in their children's education. In addition, their narratives also revealed their need for encouragement and motivation, their need for practical support in everyday school life, and their appreciation of clearly expressed expectations about education.

Gamariel, M., & Blaise, B. (2021). Studied on the Parental Influence on students' career choice and its effect on their academic performance. A case of schools in Rulindo district. The finding of the study indicated that parental variables had an effect on students' profession choices in Rulindo. These variables included the parent's greatest level of education, their employment, their expectations and beliefs and their parent child connections. The study directed that parents and children discuss higher level courses before to enrolling in them, stressing on the learner's strengths and preferences in order to lessen potential difficulties.

Chandra, G. (2018). Conducted a study on the vocational interest of secondary school student in relation to their parental factor. The result of the research revealed that there exist a strong difference in vocational interest pattern of secondary school students in terms of parental monthly income. The finding also revealed that there is a significant difference in the vocational area of secondary school students in relation to their parental educational background and profession.

Clara, A. N., Okechukwu, E., & Ugwoke, M. (2022). Conducted a research on the Parental influence and occupational choice carrier among selected Secondary School student in UYO metropolis, Nigeria. Parental influence was found to play significant role in the occupational choice made by secondary school students confirming the first research question and as anticipated; the less parentally influenced student's reported the highest mean or aspiration of students making their own occupational choice. Finding of the study further showed a significant mean difference between male and female students in their choice of occupation.

Kumar J, Panda, Dr. Antima Das, Swarnaprava Mallick, Sarojini Mishra. Studied on Parental encouragement and its impact on academic achievement. It was found that when parents actively support and motivate their children, academic success tends to flourish, fostering a positive learning environment. The parental encouragement and academic achievement of the secondary school learners have significant relation that means higher the parental encouragement, higher the academic achievement of the learners. Equally lower is the Parental encouragement; low is the academic achievement of the learners, lack of parental encouragement may hinder academic progress.

Dr. Bohane L, Nisha Bohane (2023). Conducted a study on the effect of parental encouragement on academic achievement of ninth grade students. It was found that there is significant effect of parental encourage on academic achievement of 9th grade students studying in government and private schools.

P. Ponnusamy (2021) Parental encouragement towards the academic achievement of students at higher secondary school level. The majority of student's in higher secondary school received moderate parental support for their academic achievements. They also had a level of academic achievement in their school subjects that was moderate. Private school students, according to student insights, get more parental encouragement than government school students. Likewise, females' students outperformed male students in terms of academic achievement. In general, the findings shown significant relationship between parental encouragements and student academic success.

Methodology The purpose of the present study was to explore the parental encouragement in vocational choices of senior secondary school students. For this purpose, the descriptive survey method of research was used by investigators. The present study was confined to a sample of 100 students of senior secondary school students of Jammu and Kashmir.

Population

The populations present study consist of all government and private senior secondary school students of Jammu and Kashmir.

Sampling

In the present study the investigator taken 100 Govt. and private senior secondary school students. In every school there were approximately 40 students in class 11th and 12th. Out of which 100 students were selected randomly.

Sampling technique

Stratified Random sampling technique was used for data collection.

Data collection procedure

For the present study data was collected from the six senior secondary school of district Jammu. The investigator collected data from both private and government school.

Tools Used

The data was collected by the survey method using questionnaire. In order to collected the data the investigator use the Parental Encouragement Scale (1998) by Dr Aggarwal which was modified by the investigator.

Statistics Used in the Study

For the purpose of the analysis, following appropriate and compatible statistical techniques were used. Mean, S.D, 'T' test was used.

The details of sample selected for the study is presented in table No.1

Distribution of simple

Senior secondary school students (100)

Type of school	Locality	Gender
Government (50)	Urban (20)	Boys (25)
	Rural (30)	Girls (25)
Private (50)	Urban (30)	Boys (25)
	Rural (20)	Girls (25)

Figure.1 Shows The Sample Design

Analysis

H₀₁ There exists a significant difference parental encouragement in vocational choice between boys and girls of senior secondary schools of Jammu & Kashmir.

To compare the parental encouragement in a vocational choice of boys and girls of the senior secondary school of Jammu, the score obtained by the administering parental encouragement scale (PES) was analysed using t-test. The result of the analysed data are given in table 3.1 showing the means, SD, t-value and level of significance with respect parental encouragement in vocational choice boys and girls student of Jammu

Table 3.1 means score of parental encouragement in vocational choice among boys and girls of the senior secondary school.

Variables	Total no. Of students	Means	S.D.	't' Value	Level of significance (0.05)Level
Girls	50	55.38	14.46	1.60	Not Significant
Boys	50	60.06	14.71		

Graph 3.1 shows means, S.D value of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of boys and girls of Jammu and Kashmir.

Interpretation

Table 3.1 and graph 3.2 shows the Means, S.D, t-value and level of significance of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of boys and girls of the senior secondary school of Jammu. From the table 3.1, it was found that the mean score of boys and girls are 55.38 and 60.06 respectively. The S.D of boys students is 14.71 and that of girls students is 14.46. The calculated „t“-value is 1.60 which is less than table value at 0.05 level of no significance.

Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 levels. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is rejected i.e. there is no significant difference between parental encouragement in a vocational choice of boys and girls students.

H₀₂ There is a significant difference in parental encouragement between urban and rural of senior secondary schools of Jammu & Kashmir

To study the parental encouragement in a vocational choice of urban and rural students of the senior secondary school of Jammu, the score obtained by the administering parental encouragement scale (PES) was analyzed using t-test. The result of the analyzed data is given in table 3.2 showing the means, SD, t-value and level of significance with respect parental encouragement in vocational choice urban and rural student of Jammu and Kashmir.

Table 3.2 means score of parental encouragement in vocational choice among urban and students of the senior secondary school.

variables	Total no. of student	Means	S.D	t' Value	Level of Significance (0.05 level)
urban	50	60.86	15.41	2.21	Significant
Rural	50	54.6	12.80		

Graph 3.2 shows means, S.D value of parental encouragement in vocational choice of boys and girls of Jammu and Kashmir.

Interpretation

Table 3.2 and graph 3.2 shows the Means, S.D, t-value and level of significance of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of urban and rural students of the senior secondary school of Jammu. From the table 3.2, it is found that the mean score of urban and rural are 60.86 and 54.6 respectively. The S.D of the urban student is 15.41 and that of rural students is 12.8. The calculated „t“-value is 2.21 which is greater than table value at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is significant at 0.05 levels. Therefore the alternate hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is redetected i.e. There is a significant difference between parental encouragement in a vocational choice of urban and rural students of the senior secondary school of Jammu and Kashmir.

From the mean score of parental encouragement of urban and rural students it is also found that urban students have higher mean score on parental encouragement than rural students. Hence urban students have better parental encouragement than the rural of Jammu and Kashmir.

H₀₃ There exists a significant difference in parental encouragement between government and private students of senior secondary schools of Jammu & Kashmir

To compare the parental encouragement in the vocational choice between government and private senior secondary school students of Jammu, the score obtained by the administering parental encouragement scale (PES) was analyzed using t-test. The result of the analyzed data are given in table 3.3 showing the means, SD, tvalue and level of significance with respect parental encouragement in vocational choice boys and girls student of Jammu .

Table 3.3 means score of parental encouragement in vocational choice among government and private students of the senior secondary school.

Variables	Total no. of the students	Mean	S.D	"t" value	Level of significance (0.1) level
government	50	48.68	10.59	7.75	Significant
private	50	66.68	12.70		

Graph 3.3 shows means, S.D value of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of boys and girls of Jammu and Kashmir.

Interpretation

Table 3.3 and graph 3.3 shows the no. of students, mean, S.D, t-value and level of significance of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of the senior secondary school of Jammu and Kashmir. From the table 3.3, it is found that the mean value of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of government and private school students are 48.68 and 66.68 respectively. The S.D. of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of government school student is 10.50 and the S.D parental encouragement in a vocational choice of private school is 12.70. Also, the calculated t-value is 7.75 which are more than table value at 0.01 level of significance.

Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted and i.e. there is a significant difference between parental encouragements in a vocational choice of senior secondary school student of Jammu and Kashmir.

From the mean score of parental encouragement in a vocational choice of government and private school student of Jammu and Kashmir, it is also found that parental of government school students has a low parental encouragement than private school students. Hence parental encouragements of private school students have better than government school student.

Findings

1. The findings suggested that there is a significant difference between parental encouragement in vocational choice between boys and girls of senior secondary schools of Jammu & Kashmir. The mean score of parental encouragement of boys and girls students it is also found that parental encouragement of girl's student has a low mean score as compare mean score of parental encouragement of boy's student of Jammu and Kashmir. Hence it was found the parental encouragements of boys are better parental encouragement than girl's student of students of Jammu and Kashmir.
2. The study also revealed that there was a significant difference in parental encouragement in a vocational choice of senior secondary school student of Jammu and Kashmir. It was also founded that the urban students had better parental encouragement in vocational choice than rural students. It was found that there exists significant difference in parental encouragement of urban and rural senior secondary school student of Jammu and Kashmir.
3. There is a significant difference between parental encouragement in vocation choices of government and private senior secondary school student of Jammu and Kashmir. From the mean score, the parental encouragement of government senior secondary student has low parental encouragement than the parental encouragement of a private senior secondary school student. It is found the parental encouragement in a vocational choice of private senior secondary school student better than government senior secondary school student of Jammu and Kashmir.

Conclusion From the above interpretation, it was found that parental encouragement in a vocational choice of boy's student is better than girl's student of the senior secondary school of Jammu and Kashmir. The investigator also found that there was no difference in parental encouragement in vocational choice among boys and girls student of the senior secondary school. The parental encouragement in a vocational choice of male and female and on the base of locality it was found that urban students are better than the rural students in parental encouragement of vocational choice. The study also shows that there was a significant difference between rural male and urban male as well as rural female and urban female in parental encouragement in the vocational choice the study also shows that the private students are better than Govt. students in parental encouragement of vocational choice .

Recommendations

1. Teachers and career guidance and counsellors should realise high level parental education influences students' career choice and should, therefore, pass the importance of higher education to the students in relation to their careers.
2. Parents should not force students to pursue careers similar to their own against their will. This is because the majority of the students indicated they would not choose careers similar to those of their parents.
3. Parents should realize that their values and expectations influence the career choice to a great extent. In this respect, it is recommended that parents should deliberately communicate their expectations to their children without being overly persuasive.
4. A strong parent-child relationship is essential in shaping the student's career choice. In this regard, it is recommended that parents should take time to discuss different career choices with their children. Whenever necessary, the parents should express satisfaction with the child's decision.
5. A student must not choose a vocation because he or she sees his or her friends choosing the vocation. The parents or teachers and even the child should detect his or her line of vocation from primary school by knowing his or her subjects of interest.

Suggestions for the future Study Based on the findings of the study, the researcher suggests the following areas for further research:

1. The present study was conducted over a sample of 100 senior secondary school student of Jammu. A similar type of the study can be conducted by taking a large sample in order to generalize the results.
2. The present study was conducted on senior secondary student Future studies can be done on the college and university students also
3. The study can be undertaken on various other variables like parental influence, parental involvement etc. which encourage the vocational choice of the student
4. The present study was only conducted Jammu district .similar study can be conducting the other state.

Limitation of the Study

1. The study was limited on the students of 11th and 12th class of Jammu district and did not cover the students of 9th 10th class.
2. The study was confined to the govt. and private senior secondary school of Jammu district, it can conduct of other state
3. The study was confined to 100 Govt. and private senior secondary school students, similar type of the study can be conducted large sample.

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